

THE LIFE OF ALEKSANDR FEINBERG

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Abstract: This article provides information about the life and unique creative activity of the poet Alexander Feinberg, who is Russian and Uzbek. The originality and unusualness of his poems were specially recognized.

Key words: poet, lyrics, poems, nature, originality, melody, human, life.

Alexander Arkadyevich was born on November 2, 1939 in Tashkent. His guardians moved from Novosibirsk two a long time some time recently his birth. The writer's father, Arkady Lvovich Feinberg (1891–1971), initially from Gatchina, graduated from the Organized of Innovation and worked as a chief design at a refinery. Mother Anastasia Alexandrovna (1904–?), born in Moscow, worked as a engineer in a refinery.

After completing seven a long time of school, Arkady entered the Tashkent Specialized College of Geology. After graduating from college, he served within the military in Tajikistan. After graduating from Tashkent College in 1965, he considered part-time at the News coverage Office of the Workforce of Philology and worked in a understudy daily paper. He hitched Inna Glebovna Koval in 1961

Alexander was a part of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and the creator of fifteen verse collections (counting a after death distributed two-volume work). His poems were distributed within the magazines "Queue", "Youth", "New World", "The Star of the East", "New Volga" and periodicals of remote nations:

In 1965-1969, Feinberg was a expert at the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. "Etude" (1967), "Sonia" (1969), "Sonnets" (1977), "Distant Bridges" (1978), "Reaction" (1982), "Brief Wave" (1983), "Spreading Net" (1984), the creator of "Free Pieces" (1990) and other verse collections. In Feinberg's verse, past and display, West and East patriotism and internationalism are interconnected, making a one of a kind aesthetic world.

Feinberg's expressive legend may be a individual who has completely protected his human quintessence within the age of chronicled and social arrangement, is prepared to expand a hand of sympathy and help to others, and is suffering from obnoxious occasions and occurrences happening on the globe.

The finest imaginative encounters of Russian and European artists were appeared in his idyllic work. The conventions of Eastern classical verse are not outsider to his imaginative fashion.

Scholarly interpretation is an critical portion of Feinberg's work. A writer who knows Uzbek verse impeccably, he interpreted Navoi's ghazals, lyrics and sagas of Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov, Amon Matjon and other Uzbek writers into Russian. Based on Feinberg's screenplay, "My Brother", "Beneath the Hot Sun", "Finding Individuals in Kandahar", "Criminal and Vindications" and other movies were shot at "Uzbekfilm" film studio. Four full-length include movies and almost 20 cartoons were made based on Feinberg's screenplay.

In 1999, on the event of the twentieth commemoration of the passing of the "Pakhtakor" football group in a car mischance, the film "Stadium within the Sky" was shot based on his script. In 1979, Feinberg recorded a melody around the Pakhtakor group. For several years, Feinberg driven the workshop of youthful journalists of Uzbekistan in Tashkent. Screenwriter of the film "House beneath the hot sun" (1977, "Uzbekfilm"). He passed on on October 14, 2009 in Tashkent.

He was buried within the area of the Botkin cemetery in Tashkent. "A" of G. V. Malikhina. The structure of imaginative pictures and topical dominants within the verses of A. Feinberg" (Uzbekistan National College, 2007) master's proposal is given to the think about of Feinberg's work.

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